

Sustainability of Restaurant with Service Quality and Online Promotion

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Abstract. This research explores the influence of service quality and convenience in online promotions on the sustainability of Steak Restaurants by analyzing the relationship between variables. This research aims to understand how service improvements and effective online marketing strategies contribute to customer retention and business continuity in the long term. Quantitative and qualitative research methods show that superior service quality and easy-to-use online promotions have a significant effect on customer satisfaction and loyalty. The structural model evaluation shows that service quality (SQ) and online promotion (OP) significantly influence customer satisfaction (CS), but customer satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between SQ or OP and restaurant sustainability (SUS). These findings indicate that sustainability is more influenced by external factors such as environmental awareness or regulatory incentives rather than mere customer satisfaction. The managerial implication is that restaurants need to explicitly communicate their sustainability strategies through digital promotions and transparent operational practices to enhance customer awareness and engagement with sustainability initiatives.

Keywords: Service Quality, Online Promotion, Customer Satisfaction, Sustainability

1 Introduction

The development of restaurants in Indonesia until now is believed to be one of the businesses that has quite good prospects. This restaurant uses online promotion through Instagram and several e-commerce, because in recent years, online food delivery industry has seen rapid growth into worldwide and the market size of ordering food online is increasing annually (1).

Online promotion is an important part of a restaurant because consumers must have the motivation to buy an item, so to attract consumers to buy, producers will promote their products well (2). In general, online promotion has an important role in customer satisfaction because it can increase the number of customers to the restaurant (3), so this affects the sustainability of the restaurant and increases customer loyalty.

Restaurant service quality is very important to improve service, ensure more efficient operations and reduce customer complaints. because the good quality of our service can make guests feel comfortable and guests' wishes are fulfilled. A restaurant's reputation can be strengthened through positive reviews resulting from the quality of service, both online and from direct recommendations from guests. Service quality is a significant differentiator and provides added value that makes customers feel appreciated. Restaurants with good service are also better able to handle complaints effectively, thereby improving the customer experience (4).

Sustainability in restaurants is important because it supports long-term business continuity while making a positive contribution to the environment, society and economy (5). Modern consumers are increasingly concerned about social and environmental responsibility, so restaurants that prioritize sustainability tend to be more attractive to customers. Sustainability also helps optimize operational costs through resource efficiency and creates a strong and relevant brand image in the market. Business sustainability is faced with economic fluctuations (6).

2 Literature Review

2.1 Service Quality

Service quality is an important thing for restaurants to offering products or services because of the quality of service that restaurants provide to consumers. Service quality is a comparison between reality and consumer expectations to provide quality service. Service quality at least depends on the ability to provide service to meet restaurant consumer expectations(7). Service quality is the customer's assessment of services and products, the desired level of service. Good quality service is very important because to meet customer satisfaction in order to create profits for the restaurant, the quality of this service has a big influence on customers coming back to the restaurant (8). This is to encourage customers interest in returning to the restaurant, this makes it important to improve the quality of service, this effort includes training employees to be more friendly and responsive to guests. By paying attention to service quality to increase customer satisfaction, higher loyalty and help improve the restaurant's reputation (9).

The hypothesis will be :

H1 : There is a positive relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction

H4 : There is a positive relationship between service quality and sustainability

H6 : There is a positive relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction with sustainability

2.2 Online Promotion

Promotion is a marketing strategy to provide information to customers about the value of a product or brand and invite them to buy the restaurant's products. The promotions given must be in accordance with what is being sold, so that the customers can see and expect is in accordance with their needs, so that customers do not feel disappointed. Online Promotion also has a positive influence on customer satisfaction (8).

The promotions given must be in accordance with what is being sold, so that what customers see and expect is in accordance with their wishes so that customers do not feel disappointed. This has a positive influence on customer satisfaction (8). Online promotion is a refers to the use of internet-based platforms and strategies to market products, services, or brands to a target audience (10). Online promotions have an impact on customer satisfaction because they provide convenience, personalization, interaction, and transparency that can improve the overall customer experience (11).

The hypothesis will be :

H2 : There is a positive relationship between Online promotion and Customer satisfaction

H5 : There is a positive relationship between Online Promotion and Sustainability

H7 : There is a positive relationship between Online Promotion an Customer satisfaction with sustainability

2.3 Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a way to see that a customer satisfied with the product or service the customer received. Customer satisfaction can be fulfilled if a business venture can realize several factors well for restaurant customers (8). Satisfaction is the result of consumers' assessment of the products or services provided by restaurant servers. Customers are people who can enjoy the value offered by the restaurant and must offer more value than competitors so that customers can make choices based on that value. offered. Customer satisfaction is the buyer's assessment of the offer. the seller as perceived by the customer (12). Customer satisfaction can increase customer loyalty to a restaurant, because customer satisfaction is one of the important things for a restaurant to sustain (13).

The hypothesis will be :

H3 : There is a positive relationship between customer satisfaction with sustainability

2.4 Sustainability

Researchers have found a general need to improve education in hospitality sustainability by providing training on sustainability, a study on positive consumer perceptions of the image of green hotels related to their perceptions and environmental initiatives also found that customer satisfaction has an impact on a restaurant's sustainability performance (14).

Customer satisfaction affects the sustainability performance of a restaurant. To research the industry is growing, sustainable restaurants are still an important thing for a very unclear concept. To develop sustainability can create comprehensive sustainability initiatives restaurant owners and operators (15).

3 Methodology

To identify and analyze restaurant sustainability with service quality and online promotions. This approach was chosen because it is able to provide measurable and relevant data to answer research questions systematically. The population in this research is restaurant customers who are affected by online promotions with samples taken using purposive sampling techniques based on certain criteria, such as customers who have made purchases through online promotions. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire with a Likert scale of 1 – 5 which was designed to measure the variables of service quality, convenience of online promotions, and restaurant preferences.

Measurements for each variable are taken from, Service quality has 5 indicators, namely : Tangible (physical evidence), Reliability (reliability), Responsiveness (responsiveness), Assurance (guarantee), Empathy (empathy) (16). The ease of online promotion has 3 indicators, namely service availability information, service responsiveness, purchase transaction process and use of information (17). The sustainability of the b steak restaurant has 3 indicators, namely customer loyalty, Cost reduction, profit growth (18). Customer satisfaction has 3 indicators, namely Customer expectations are proportional to the quality of service provided, Performance on the quality of services provided, Response to the quality of services provided by the restaurant (19).

4 Result and Discussion

A construct within a structural framework could potentially be impacted by various other variables. The Measurement Model evaluation was carried out with a specific focus on the validation of constructs through the analysis of discriminant and convergent validity, alongside construct reliability. The latter was evaluated using a Composite Reliability (CR) metric. CR values ranging from 0.797 to 0.907, while AVE values range from 0.878 to 0.941. The results presented demonstrate satisfactory reliability and validity as the assessed metrics displayed adequate values. The findings indicate that the study has achieved a satisfactory level of convergent validity, as all CR values exceed the threshold of 0.7, and AVE values are above 0.5. This suggests that the constructs adequately explain the variance in their indicators, confirming the robustness of the measurement model in assessing Customer Satisfaction (CS), Online Promotion (OP), Service Quality (SQ), and Sustainability (SUS). The measurement model for the relationship between variables in Figure 1 is visually used for research with each indicator.

Fig. 1. Structural Model Evaluation Path Diagram

Table 1 presents the hypothesis testing results, including standardized coefficients (STD), standard deviation (STDV), t-statistics (T-Stat), p-values.

Hypothesis	STD	STDV	T-Stat	P-Value	Result
H1 : SQ-CS	0.378	0.137	2.765	0.006	Supported
H2 : OP-CS	0.687	0.133	5.154	0.000	Supported
H3 : SUS-CS	-0.125	0.092	1.350	0.178	Supported
H4 : SQ-SUS	0.530	0.192	2.755	0.006	Supported
H5 : OP-SUS	0.347	0.193	1.798	0.073	Not Supported
H6 : SQ-CS-SUS	-0.066	0.070	0.943	0.346	Not Supported
H7 : OP-CS-SUS	-0.043	0.039	1.100	0.272	Not Supported

TABLE I. STRUCTURAL MODEL EVALUATION

The structural model evaluation reveals that both service quality (SQ) and online promotion (OP) significantly influence customer satisfaction (CS) as shown in table 1, by the support for H1 (SQ - CS: $T = 2.765$, $p = 0.006$) and H2 (OP - CS: $T = 5.154$, $p = 0.000$). These findings align with established theories emphasizing the role of service quality in fostering consumer contentment, particularly in hospitality contexts (20). Similarly, the strong impact of online promotion on satisfaction reflects the growing importance of digital engagement in shaping consumer perceptions, as noted by Noori (21), who highlighted the role of e-service quality in driving positive user experiences. Furthermore, H4 (SQ - SUS: $T = 2.755$, $p = 0.006$) demonstrates that service quality

directly enhances restaurant sustainability (SUS), suggesting that operational excellence in service delivery contributes to long-term environmental and economic resilience. This resonates with Perrigot et al (22) assertion that sustainable practices in restaurants, such as waste reduction and ethical sourcing, are often intertwined with high service standards.

However, the study challenges conventional assumptions about the mediating role of sustainability on customer satisfaction outcomes. H3 (SUS - CS: $T = 1.350$, $p = 0.178$) and H5 (OP - SUS: $T = 1.798$, $p = 0.073$) were not supported, indicating that satisfied customers do not necessarily translate to sustainable outcomes, nor does online promotion directly drive sustainability. This contrasts with Hashish et al. (23) findings in green hospitality, where satisfaction mediated sustainability intentions. The lack of mediation in H6 (SQ - CS - SUS: $T = 0.943$, $p = 0.346$) and H7 (OP - CS - SUS: $T = 1.100$, $p = 0.272$) further suggests that customer satisfaction alone is insufficient to bridge service quality or promotional efforts to sustainability. This may imply that sustainability adoption requires extrinsic motivators, such as environmental awareness or regulatory incentives, beyond mere satisfaction (24).

5 Conclusions

The structural model evaluation confirms that service quality (SQ) and operational performance (OP) significantly impact customer satisfaction (CS). Additionally, SQ directly influences sustainability (SUS), reinforcing the role of high service standards in fostering long-term business resilience. However, the study finds that customer satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between service quality, operational performance, and sustainability were not supported. This suggests that while satisfied customers are crucial for business success, sustainability initiatives require additional drivers beyond mere satisfaction, such as regulatory support or environmental awareness. These findings highlight the importance of integrating explicit sustainability strategies, such as transparent communication and digital engagement, rather than relying solely on service improvements or promotional efforts. Future research should explore how external motivators, including social norms and ethical values, influence sustainable consumer behavior to develop more effective sustainability-driven business models.

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